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Short story as literary genre in American literature.

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Abstract. The short story, as a literary genre, has played a crucial role in shaping the trajectory of American literature. From its early roots in the 19th century to its modern iterations, this compact form has captivated readers with its ability to convey deep emotional and intellectual insights within a limited narrative framework.

Throughout American literary history, authors have used the short story to explore a wide range of themes—supernatural, psychological, and social—offering glimpses into the complexities of the human experience. Writers like Washington Irving, Nathaniel Hawthorne, and Edgar Allan Poe helped define the genre in its early stages, while later figures such as Flannery O'Connor and Raymond Carver expanded its scope.

This article will explore the development of the short story in American literature, tracing its evolution from early pioneers to contemporary masters. By examining the unique characteristics of the genre and highlighting its major contributors, we will gain a deeper understanding of its significance and enduring appeal in American storytelling.

Key words: Short story, American literature, Washington Irving, Nathaniel Hawthorne, Edgar Allan Poe, Realism, Modernism, John Steinbeck, Social critique, Human condition.

СТУДЕНТ ВТОРОГО КУРСА МАГИСТРАТУРЫ UZSWLU

Аннотация. Короткий рассказ как литературный жанр сыграл решающую роль в формировании траектории американской литературы. От своих ранних корней в 19 веке до современных итераций эта компактная форма пленила читателей своей способностью передавать глубокие эмоциональные и интеллектуальные прозрения в ограниченных повествовательных рамках.

На протяжении всей истории американской литературы авторы использовали короткий рассказ для исследования широкого спектра тем — сверхъестественных, психологических и социальных — предлагая проблески в сложности человеческого опыта.

Такие писатели, как Вашингтон Ирвинг, Натаниэль Готорн и Эдгар Аллан По, помогли определить жанр на ранних этапах, в то время как более поздние деятели, такие как Фланнери О'Коннор и Рэймонд Карвер, расширили его сферу. В этой статье будет рассмотрено развитие короткого рассказа в американской литературе, прослеживается его эволюция от ранних пионеров до современных мастеров. Изучая уникальные

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характеристики жанра и выделяя его основных участников, мы глубже поймем его значимость и неизменную привлекательность в американском повествовании.

Ключевые слова: *короткий рассказ, американская литература, Вашингтон Ирвинг, Натаниэль Готорн, Эдгар Аллан По, реализм, модернизм, Джон Стейнбек, социальная критика, состояние человека.*

Origins and Early Development of the Short Story in American Literature

The short story in American literature has its origins in the early 19th century, paralleling the rise of the periodical press. As magazines and newspapers became more widespread, there was a growing demand for shorter works that could be easily consumed by readers. This shift in publishing helped give rise to the short story as a popular and accessible form. Early American writers, such as Washington Irving, Nathaniel Hawthorne, and Edgar Allan Poe, were instrumental in defining the genre's parameters.

Washington Irving's *The Sketch Book* (1820) featured some of the first successful American short stories, including "Rip Van Winkle" and "The Legend of Sleepy Hollow." Irving's works were characterized by their blend of humor, folklore, and a distinctly American setting, laying the foundation for the genre. Nathaniel Hawthorne followed with *Twice-Told Tales* (1837), offering stories that often delved into the darker aspects of human nature, morality, and guilt. Edgar Allan Poe, however, is perhaps the most famous figure of this early period, particularly for his ability to craft stories of psychological intensity, horror, and mystery. Poe's short stories, such as "The Tell-Tale Heart" and "The Fall of the House of Usher," set a standard for the genre's economy of language and emotional impact.

These early writers not only established the conventions of the short story—brevity, a singular focus on plot or character, and a tightly woven structure—but they also demonstrated the flexibility of the genre in addressing a variety of themes, from the fantastical to the moral and the psychological.

The Evolution of the Genre: Realism and Modernism

As the 19th century progressed and America entered the 20th, the short story evolved to reflect the changing social and political realities of the country. The rise of realism and modernism introduced new themes and styles, with writers like Henry James, Mark Twain, and Kate Chopin using the short story to explore the complexities of American life.

In the hands of Twain, the short story became a tool for social satire, as seen in "The Celebrated Jumping Frog of Calaveras County," where humor and wit exposed the quirks and

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contradictions of American society. Kate Chopin's work, such as "The Story of an Hour," brought a focus on women's experiences and the constraints of societal expectations. Her stories often questioned traditional gender roles and provided insight into the emotional lives of women.

By the time of modernism in the early 20th century, writers like F. Scott Fitzgerald, Ernest Hemingway, and William Faulkner began to experiment with the form. Hemingway, in particular, became known for his sparse, minimalist prose that nonetheless conveyed profound emotional depth. His short stories, such as "Hills Like White Elephants" and "A Clean, Well-Lighted Place," exemplified his "iceberg theory" of writing, where the underlying meaning of the story is not immediately obvious but subtly implied beneath the surface.

Post-War American Short Story: Social Commentary and Psychological Depth

The post-war period brought new concerns to American short fiction, with writers focusing on social commentary, psychological depth, and the struggles of modern life. John Cheever and J.D. Salinger used the short story to explore the tensions of suburban life, alienation, and disillusionment in post-war America. Cheever's stories, often set in the suburbs, revealed the hidden anxieties and moral conflicts beneath the veneer of middle-class respectability.

Flannery O'Connor, one of the genre's most significant voices, used the short story to explore themes of religion, morality, and the grotesque, often with a Southern Gothic flavor. Her stories, like "A Good Man is Hard to Find" and "Everything That Rises Must Converge," juxtaposed violence and grace, offering a distinct theological vision through her characters' extreme situations.

In the later 20th century, authors like Raymond Carver brought the short story back to its minimalist roots. Carver's stories, such as those found in "What We Talk About When We Talk About Love" (1981), dealt with the small, often bleak moments of everyday life, focusing on the disconnection and despair found in ordinary interactions. His pared-down prose and focus on working-class characters made him one of the most influential short story writers of the modern era.

John Steinbeck's Contribution to the American Short Story

Amid these developments, John Steinbeck stands as a key figure whose work in the short story genre reflects both the social concerns of his time and a deep empathy for the struggles of ordinary people. Steinbeck's short stories, like his novels, are marked by a profound interest in the human condition, particularly the plight of the working class and marginalized individuals.

Steinbeck's "The Long Valley" (1938), a collection of short stories, showcases his mastery of the form. Stories like "The Chrysanthemums" and "Flight" examine themes of isolation,

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frustration, and the struggle for personal dignity. Steinbeck's ability to imbue his characters with emotional depth, while maintaining a clear-eyed view of social realities, gives his stories a unique resonance. His short fiction often reflects the broader concerns found in his novels, such as in *The Grapes of Wrath* (1939), but within the condensed, powerful structure of the short story.

Steinbeck's stories are also notable for their rich sense of place. Whether set in the fertile valleys of California or the rugged landscape of the American West, his stories often use the environment as a backdrop for exploring the characters' internal struggles, creating a sense of harmony between setting and theme.

Conclusion

The Short Story's Enduring Legacy in American Literature

The American short story has continually evolved, adapting to the changing concerns and sensibilities of different eras. From its early origins with Irving and Poe to its modern expressions in the works of Carver and O'Connor, the short story remains a powerful and versatile literary form. Its brevity and focus allow for intense explorations of character, theme, and emotion, often leaving a lasting impression on the reader.

John Steinbeck's contribution to the short story genre is a testament to its potential for both social critique and emotional depth. By examining the lives of ordinary people, he captured the heart of the American experience, using the short story as a vehicle to convey timeless themes of struggle, resilience, and empathy. The short story, as a genre, continues to hold a vital place in American literature, offering new generations of writers a flexible, impactful form for exploring the complexities of life in all its varied dimensions.

REFERENCES

1. Baym, Nina, et al. *The Norton Anthology of American Literature*. W.W. Norton & Company, 2012.
2. Bendixen, Alfred, and James Nagel, editors. *A Companion to the American Short Story*. Wiley-Blackwell, 2010.
3. May, Charles E. *The Short Story: The Reality of Artifice*. Twayne Publishers, 1995.
4. O'Connor, Flannery. *Mystery and Manners: Occasional Prose*. Farrar, Straus, and Giroux, 1969.
5. Steinbeck, John. *The Long Valley*. Viking Press, 1938.
6. Poe, Edgar Allan. *The Fall of the House of Usher and Other Writings*. Penguin Classics, 2003.

• ZAMONAVIY ILM-FAN VA TA'LIM ISTIQBOLLARI •
ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYASI

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7. Fitzgerald, F. Scott. The Short Stories of F. Scott Fitzgerald: A New Collection. Scribner, 1989.
8. Cowan, Michael H. Twentieth-Century American Short Stories. McGraw-Hill, 1993.

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